

MAQOLA TARIXI

Qabul qilindi: 15-Yanvar 2022
Ma'qullandi: 20- Yanvar 2022
Chop etildi: 25- Yanvar 2022

KALIT SO'ZLAR

Dirixle integrali, Eyley-Puasson integrali, Laplas integrallari, Frenelli integrallari

1. Dirixle integrali.

Ushbu $J = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\sin x}{x} dx$ Dirixle

integralini hisoblashning juda ko'p usullari mavjud. Biz ushbu Dirixle integralining qiymatini parametr ga bog'liq integrallar yordamida hisoblaymiz. Buning uchun

$$J_{\alpha} = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\sin \alpha x}{x} dx, (\alpha > 0)$$

integralni qaraymiz.

Bu integralni α parametr bo'yicha differensiallab hisoblaymiz. Ammo, α bo'yicha differensiallasak,

$$\frac{dJ_{\alpha}}{d\alpha} = \int_0^{\infty} \cos \alpha x dx$$

integral Leybnits qoidasiga ko'ra uzoqlashuvchi bo'ladi. Shu sababli, e^{-kx} , $k > 0$ "yaqinlashtiruvchi

PARAMETRGA BOG'LIQ INTEGRALLAR YORDAMIDA AYRIM MUHIM INTEGRALLARNI HISOBLASH USULLARI

Norjigitov Husan¹, Dustnazarova Iroda²,

Mirhaydarov Muhiddin³

¹ fizika-matematika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent, Guliston davlat universiteti, O'zbekiston, Guliston,

² o'qituvchi, Guliston davlat universiteti, O'zbekiston, Guliston,

³ magistr, Guliston davlat universiteti, O'zbekiston, Guliston

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5910196>

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada juda ko'p sohalarida muhim hisoblangan ayrim xosmas integrallar: Dirixle integrali, Eyley-Puasson integrali, Laplas integrallari, Frenelli integrallari yaqinlashishga tekshirilgan va ularning qiymatlarini hisoblash usullari o'rganilgan. Ularning qiymatlarini hisoblashda parametr ga bog'liq integrallarning xossaligidan foydalanilgan.

ko'paytuvchi" tushunchasini kiritamiz. Buning uchun ushbu

$$J_k(\alpha) = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-kx} \frac{\sin \alpha x}{x} dx, (\alpha \geq 0, k > 0)$$

funksiyani

$J_k(\alpha)$ funksiyadan α bo'yicha xususiy hosila olib, quyidagini topamiz:

$$\frac{\partial J_k(\alpha)}{\partial \alpha} = \int_0^{\infty} e^{-kx} \cos \alpha x dx = I.$$

Yuqoridagi integralda integral ostidagi funksiya $\alpha \in [0, \infty)$ da har doim mavjud va integral yaqinlashuvchi bo'ladi. Uni ikki marta bo'laklab integrallash orqali

$$I = \frac{k}{\alpha^2 + k^2}$$

ekanligini topamiz.

Shunday qilib,

$$\frac{\partial J_k(\alpha)}{\partial \alpha} = \frac{k}{\alpha^2 + k^2}.$$

Bundan,

$$J_k(\alpha) = \text{arctg} \frac{\alpha}{k} + C$$

bo'lishi kelib chiqadi.

$$J_k(0) = 0 \text{ munosabatdan } C = 0 \text{ va}$$

$$J_k(\alpha) = \text{arctg} \frac{\alpha}{k} \text{ ekanligi kelib chiqadi.}$$

Agar $\alpha = \text{const}$ bo'lsa, unda $J_k(\alpha)$ ifoda k ning funksiyasi bo'lib qoladi. Agar $k \rightarrow +0$ da limitga o'tsak, u holda

$$J_\alpha = \lim_{k \rightarrow +0} J_k(\alpha) = \lim_{k \rightarrow +0} \left(\text{arctg} \frac{\alpha}{k} \right) = \frac{\pi}{2}$$

tenglikka ega bo'lamiz.

Xususan, $\alpha = 1$ bo'lganda

$$J_1 = J = \int_0^\infty \frac{\sin x}{x} dx = \frac{\pi}{2}$$

ekanligi kelib chiqadi.

2. Eyler-Puasson integrali.

$$\begin{aligned} J^2 &= \int_0^\infty dt \left(\int_0^\infty e^{-(1+t^2)n^2} ndn \right) = \int_0^\infty dt \left(\frac{1}{2} \int_0^\infty e^{-(1+t^2)n^2} d(1+n^2) \right) = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^\infty dt \left(-\frac{1}{1+t^2} e^{-(1+t^2)n} \Big|_0^\infty \right) = \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \int_0^\infty \frac{1}{1+t^2} dt = \frac{1}{2} \text{arctgt} \Big|_0^\infty = \frac{\pi}{4} \end{aligned}$$

Bundan

$$J = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2}$$

tenglik o'rinli ekanligi kelib chiqadi.

3. Laplas integrallari.

Ushbu

$$L_1 = \int_0^\infty \frac{\cos \beta x}{\alpha^2 + x^2} dx$$

va

$$L_2 = \int_0^\infty \frac{x \sin \beta x}{\alpha^2 + x^2} dx, \quad (\alpha, \beta > 0)$$

integrallar Laplas integrallari deb ataladi.

Ushbu

$$\text{Bu bandda ushbu } J = \int_0^\infty e^{-x^2} dx -$$

Eyler-Puasson integralining qiymatini hisoblash bilan shug'ullanamiz. Buning uchun, dastlab $x = nt$ almashtirish bajaramiz, bu yerda n ixtiyoriy musbat son. U holda

$$J = n \cdot \int_0^\infty e^{-n^2 t^2} dt$$

tenglik o'rinli bo'ladi. Tenglikning har ikkala tomoniga e^{-n^2} ifodani ko'paytirib, so'ngra 0 dan ∞ gacha n bo'yicha integrallab, quyidagi

$$J \cdot \int_0^\infty e^{-n^2} dn = \int_0^\infty e^{-n^2} n dn \int_0^\infty e^{-n^2 t^2} dt$$

yoki

$$J = \int_0^\infty n e^{-n^2} dn \int_0^\infty e^{n^2 t^2} dt$$

tenglikni hosil qilamiz. Oxirgi integralni hisoblashda o'zgaruvchilarni o'rinlarini almashtirib, quyidagini hosil qilamiz:

$$\int_0^\infty e^{-t(\alpha^2 + x^2)} dt = \frac{1}{\alpha^2 + x^2}$$

tenglikdan foydalanib,

$$L_1 = \int_0^\infty \cos \beta x dx \int_0^\infty e^{-t(\alpha^2 + x^2)} dt$$

tenglikni hosil qilamiz. Integrallash tartibini o'zgartirib, quyidagi

$$L_1 = \int_0^\infty e^{-\alpha^2 t} dt \left(\int_0^\infty e^{-tx^2} \cos \beta x dx \right) = \int_0^\infty J(t) \cdot e^{-\alpha^2 t} dt$$

tenglikni hosil qilamiz. Bu yerda

$$J(t) = \int_0^\infty e^{-tx^2} \cos \beta x dx$$

integralni hisoblash usuli [2] da ko'rsatilganiga ko'ra,

$$J(t) = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{t}} \cdot e^{-\frac{\beta^2}{4t}}$$

munosabatni topamiz. U holda [2] ga ko'ra,

$$L_1 = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{2} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-\alpha^2 t - \frac{\beta^2}{4t}} \cdot \frac{dt}{\sqrt{t}}$$

bo'ladi.

Agar $t = z^2$ almashtirishni kiritsak,

$$L_1 = \sqrt{\pi} \cdot \int_0^{\infty} e^{-\alpha^2 z^2 - \frac{\beta^2}{4z^2}} dz = e^{-2\alpha\beta} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-\left(\alpha z - \frac{\beta}{z}\right)^2} dz = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{\alpha} e^{-\alpha\beta} \cdot \int_0^{\infty} e^{-y^2} dy = \frac{\sqrt{\pi}}{\alpha} e^{-\alpha\beta}$$

munosabatni hosil qilamiz.

Shunday qilib,

$$L_1 = \frac{\pi}{2\alpha} \cdot e^{-\alpha\beta}$$

tenglik o'rinli bo'lar ekan.

Agar

$$L_2 = -\frac{dL_1}{d\beta}$$

munosabatni inobatga olsak, L_2 uchun ushbu tenglikka ega bo'lamiz:

$$L_2 = \frac{\pi}{2} e^{-\alpha\beta}$$

4. Frenelli integrallari.

Ushbu

$$F_1 = \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\sin t}{\sqrt{t}} dt = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^{\infty} \sin t dt \int_0^{\infty} e^{-n^2} dn = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^{\infty} dn \left(\int_0^{\infty} e^{-n^2} \sin t dt \right) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{dn}{1+n^2} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \cdot \frac{\pi}{2\sqrt{2}} = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}}$$

tenglikni hosil qilamiz.

$$F_1 = \int_0^{\infty} \sin x^2 dx \quad \text{va} \quad F_2 = \int_0^{\infty} \cos x^2 dx$$

integrallar Frenelli integrallari deb ataladi.

Quyidagi

$$|\sin x^2| \leq 1, \quad |\cos x^2| \leq 1$$

tengsizliklar o'rinli bo'lganligi sababli F_1

va F_2 integrallar yaqinlashuvchi

integrallardir. Ularning qiymatini hisoblash

uchun $x^2 = 2\alpha t$ almashtirish bajaramiz. Hosil

bo'lgan

$$F_1 = \int_0^{\infty} \sin x^2 dx = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\sin t}{\sqrt{t}} dt \quad \text{va}$$

$$F_2 = \int_0^{\infty} \cos x^2 dx = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{\infty} \frac{\cos t}{\sqrt{t}} dt$$

integrallar ostidagi $\frac{1}{\sqrt{t}}$ ifodani quyidagi

integral bilan almashtiramiz:

$$\frac{1}{\sqrt{t}} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-m^2} dn$$

Natijada quyidagi tenglik hosil bo'ladi:

$$\int_0^{\infty} \frac{\sin t}{\sqrt{t}} dt = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^{\infty} \sin t dt \int_0^{\infty} e^{-m^2} dn$$

Oxirgi integralda integrallarning o'zgaruvchilarini almashtiramiz:

Xuddi shuningdek, ushbu tenglikni hosil

$$\text{qilamiz} \quad F_2 = \sqrt{\frac{\pi}{2}}$$

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR:

1. Sh. O.Alimov, R.R.Ashurov. Matematik analiz. 1-3 jildlar. – Toshkent, Mumtoz so'z, 2018.
2. Г.М.Фихтенгольц. Курс дифференциального и интегрального исчисления. В 3 т. Т. II, – 8-е изд. М.: ФИЗМАТЛИТ, 2003, 864 с.